

from a stock culture, at 5 nymphs/seedling. Plant damage was measured (Standard evaluation system for rice 0 to 9 scale) 10 d after infestation, when all TN1 seedlings were killed.

All test varieties except IR64 were susceptible (see table). IR64, which exhibited moderate resistance, is not grown in Bangladesh.

We screened 18 BRRI elite breeding lines, 41 promising exotic varieties, and 23 local germplasm collections using the same procedure. Only BR1711-7-24-2

Reaction of BR and IR varieties to WBPH in Bangladesh. BRRI, Gazipur, 1987.

Variety	Plant damage score ^a	Reaction ^b
BR1	9.0	S
BR2	8.3	S
BR3	7.7	S
BR4	8.3	S
BR5	9.0	S
BR6	9.0	S
BR7	8.3	S
BR8	7.0	S
BR9	7.0	S
BR10	8.3	S
BR11	7.7	S
BR12	7.7	S
BR14	7.7	S
BR15	8.3	S
BR16	7.7	S
BR17	9.0	S
BR18	7.7	S
BR19	9.0	S
BR20	9.0	S
BR21	9.0	S
IR5	8.3	S
IR8	9.0	S
IR20	9.0	S
IR22	9.0	S
IR24	9.0	S
IR26	9.0	S
IR28	7.7	S
IR29	8.3	S
IR30	8.3	S
IR32	8.3	S
IR34	8.3	S
IR36	8.3	S
IR38	8.3	S
IR40	9.0	S
IR42	9.0	S
IR44	7.7	S
IR45	7.0	S
IR46	7.0	S
IR50	7.7	S
IR52	7.0	S
IR56	6.3	MS
IR64	5.0	MR

^aAverage of 3 sets, scored on a scale of 0-9
^bS = susceptible, MS = moderately susceptible, R = moderately resistant.

and BR2070-15-6, exotic variety Lua Ngu (Vietnam), and local varieties Rajasail 3 and Rajasail 8 (BRRI acc. no. 2436 and 2440) were moderately resistant.

While varieties with moderate resistance may be planted if WBPH incidence is low, the breeding lines identified will require further

improvement and evaluation before they can be released.

Babawee, Hondarwala, Rathu Heenati, and Gangala are resistant to WBPH at IRRI, but susceptible at BRRI. Further studies are needed to determine whether the differential varietal reactions are due to differences in WBPH populations. □

A potential donor for resistance to the gall midge (GM) population of Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh

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We evaluated four donors and two derivatives against the GM population of Srikakulam during rainy season 1988. Twenty-day-old seedlings of each entry were planted in 3-m rows at 15- × 15-cm spacing. GM incidence was recorded

in 21 hills at 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT).

Only Banglei showed no GM (see table), and could be a donor for resistance to the GM population of Srikakulam District. The other potential donors (Eswarakora, Leaug 152, and Velluthacheera) showed no resistance. The two GM-resistant derivatives, W 1263 (MTU 15/ Eswarakora) and Phalguna (IR8/Siam 29), also did not show resistance reaction to the local GM population.

In view of these reactions of proven donors and derivatives, we strongly suspect the existence of a new GM biotype in the district. □

Reaction of donors and derivatives to GM. Srikakulam District, A. P., India, 1988.

Variety	Parentage	GM incidence (%)			
		30 DT		50 DT	
		Hill	Tiller	Hill	Tiller
Eswarakora	Donor	23.8	2.9	47.6	3.1
W1263	MTUIS/Eswarakora	38.1	5.5	81.0	9.8
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	42.9	7.5	90.5	24.1
Leaug 152	Donor	28.6	4.5	85.7	13.9
Velluthacheera	Donor	9.5	1.0	57.1	6.2
Banglei	Donor	0	0	0	0
TN1	Susceptible check	69.0	8.9	100.0	27.2

Screening for resistance to rice gall midge (GM)

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason is a major pest in India. This pest attacks the

rice crop in the plateau region of Bihar, both upland and lowland. Six GM biotypes have been identified (one each in China, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and in Andhra Pradesh and Orissa in India). The biotype at Ranchi appears to be different (Table 1).

In 1986 wet season, 60 rice genotypes received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad,

Table 1. Reaction of the Ranchi GM biotype and of 6 established biotypes to 5 differential varieties.

Origin	Reaction ^a				
	Eswarakora group	Siam 29	OB677 derivative	PTB derivative	Leaug 152
China	R	R	R	S	—
Indonesia	S	R	R	S	R
Sri Lanka	S	R	R	R	R
India (Andhra Pradesh)	R	R	R	R	R
India (Orissa)	S	R	R	R	R
Thailand	R	S	S	S	S
India (Ranchi)	R	S	S	MR	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Evaluation of rice cultivars for field resistance to GM.

Score ^a	Cultivars
0	RP1579-92-85-203
1	RP2199-3-3-5-1, RP2190-104-64-18-1, RP2434-24-2-2, Phalguna
3	RP2235-163-33-8, RP2235-48-54-6, RP2091-272-34-8, WGL 48684, R270-3188, RP2431-6-62, RP2434-79-2-6
5	Rp1125-606-637-1, W1125-630-667~1, RP1125-638-1-1, RTN81, RP2435-50-1, RP2434-24-1-2, RP2434-22-3-3, RP1579-34-54, RP2235-136-65-10, RP2235-91-15-1, RP1579-43, RP1579-43-48, CR400-16, CR406-16, OR447-3, RP2199-32-30-47-46, RP1607-1629-44-221, RP1606-29-232, RP2431-5-3-4
7	RP1125-604-1-1, RP1125-637-673-1, RP2199-84-2, WGL 44645, RP2432-34-3-1, RP2432-34-3-4, RP2434-22-3-2, RP1579-38-48, RP1579-36-33, RP2235-85-62-8, RP2235-62-33-1, RP2199-34-6-1, CR404-6, CR400-15, CR404-9-1, R278-3528, OR633-7, RP2199-3-3-3-2, RP1528-86-43-220, RP1579-59-227, RP2434-79-2-4, RP2434-22-3-3, Vikas
9	RP2432-34-4-5, RP2432-34-5-4, OR706-4, RP2432-34-3-4, RP2432-34-5-1, Jaya

^aBased on *Standard evaluation system for rice scale*.

were screened against GM. The genotypes were sown in 4.50- × 2.0-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 2 replications. All recommended agronomic cultural practices were used.

Maximum GM infestation was in the last week of Sep to the first week of Oct. At 50 d after transplanting, 15 randomly selected hills were scored for number of hills having silvershoot and for number of silvershoots/infested hill. Susceptible checks Jaya and Vikas had severe infestation (more than 40%).

No silvershoots were found in RP1579-92-85-203. Resistance levels of cultivars are given in Table 2. Cultivars scoring 0-3 can be used as donor parents in the breeding programs. □

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Resistance of rice varieties to brown planthopper (BPH), whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), and gall midge (GM) in India

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BPH, WBPH, and GM cause substantial yield losses in Chattisgarh region (the rice bowl of Madhya Pradesh State). We screened about 400 accessions using the standard seedbox screening technique at Hyderabad 1983-87. For BPH and WBPH, damage was scored on the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale* 1-9; absence of silvershoots was rated resistant to GM.

Entries with damage scores 5 or lower in replicated tests are presented in the table. Most of these varieties possess resistance to one pest; Bhakwa was resistant to both BPH and GM. □

Test lines with damage scores of 5.0 or lower against BPH, WBPH, and GM at Hyderabad, India.

Accession no.	Cultivar	Damage score
<i>Brown planthopper</i>		
A440	Anjania	4.1
A61 _i	Bainspath	5.0
B2112	Bhakwa	5.0
C62 _{iii}	Chhatri	3.8
---	E.B. 17	4.7
K2351	Kabari	2.0
L289 _{ii}	Lalbasant	4.1
S644	Safedhdhanwar	1.9
<i>Whitebacked planthopper</i>		
	Batri	2.9
D307 _i	Dihula	3.0
DI061	Dihula	2.8
DI064	Dihula	2.7
---	Karanphool	3.0
---	Khalasu	2.0
<i>Gall midge</i>		
B2712	Bhakwa	Resistant
	Dehradodi	Resistant
	Gurmatia	Resistant
	Jhitpiti	Resistant
	Kudunjan	Resistant
	Lalbogri	Resistant
	Tulasimanjari	Resistant
	Viruppu	Resistant

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